

RELATIVE INFLUENCE OF WORKPLACE SAFETY AND CONFLICT MANAGEMENT ON JOB PERFORMANCE OF UNIVERSITY NON-TEACHING STAFF IN SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relative influence of workplace safety and conflict management on the job performance of university non-teaching staff in southwestern Nigeria. This study adopted the descriptive survey research design to establish the relationship that exists between the independent and dependent variables. The study sample was drawn from public universities in the southwestern states of Nigeria. This sample, thus drawn, formed the participant respondents in the study to which the research instruments were administered.

The target population of the study consisted of 10,348 senior non-teaching staff of both the federal and state universities in southwestern Nigeria. This population was in focus because of the significant role the senior non-teaching staff plays in the achievement of university goals and objectives. Again, in most universities, the population of the non-teaching staff is larger; thus, this population cannot be underplayed in the attainment of universities' vision and mission. The study adopted the multi-stage sampling procedure. In the first stage, the simple random sampling technique was adopted to select five out of six states which represented eighty percent (80%) of states in southwestern Nigeria. In the second stage, stratified random sampling technique was used to sort federal and state universities into strata. Fifteen percent (15%) of the senior non-teaching staff, which is 1,142 respondents, were selected out of 7,607 total numbers of senior non-teaching staff. The Conflict management scale and Senior Non-Teaching Staff Job Performance Questionnaire were adapted from the harmonised annual performance evaluation reports of sampled public universities to elicit responses from senior non-teaching staff. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to answer research question 1, while research question 2 was answered using Multiple Regression Analysis at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

There is no significant relationship between conflict management and job performance ($r = 0.06$; $p > 0.05$) of senior non-teaching staff in public universities in southwestern Nigeria. However, there is a significant relationship between workplace safety and job performance ($r = 0.06$; $p > 0.05$) of senior non-teaching staff in public universities in southwestern Nigeria.

Results reveal that there is no significant relative contribution of conflict management to job performance ($\beta = -0.05$; $t = -1.04$; $p > 0.05$), and there is no significant relative contribution of workplace safety to job performance of the senior non-teaching staff ($\beta = -0.04$; $t = -0.69$; $p > 0.05$). It was recommended that senior non-teaching staff should be encouraged to put in more effort in their job performance as their salary level increases. Attention should be paid to maintaining the practice of conflict management among senior non-teaching staff as it has been proven based on the study that it enhances job performance.

Keywords: Conflict Management, Workplace Safety, Job Performance

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INTRODUCTION

Job performance is concerned with employees' skills and abilities demonstrated in achieving everyday job value as expected in line with an organisation's prescribed procedure and time frame. In the same way Jayeoba et al (2021) describe job performance as a multi-faceted construct which highlights both actions and behaviours directly under employees' control and contribute to the goals of organizations. Employees' performance embody an all-encompassing ideology of employees in relation to their behaviour, quality and quantity performance, activities and aids towards achieving an organisation's vision, mission and goals (Inuwa and Muhammad, 2016). Similarly, Inuwa (2016) affirmed that employees' performance is a key edifice of an organisation, in that, as employees' performance increases so does the organisation's overall performance rises. Therefore, employers of labour have realised the importance of employees' job performance in realisation of goals and visions in their organisations, industries or companies within a competitive global market.

Job performance is believed to be a strong link made up of strategic goals of the employee, customer satisfaction, economic contributions and outcomes of work (Roseline and Felicia, 2015). Wang (2010) also opined that job performance measurement in universities focuses much on output and outcome measurements, which are able to capture the whole process of university employees' activities from input, process to output or outcome. Universities are not guided by principles of profit maximisation solely as most organisations are in the private sector. They may have no priorities in mind in terms of aggressive resource seeking, cost reduction and profit generation. However, universities have tried to maintain a stable status of operating and by that they slowly achieve institutional objectives. Thus, non-teaching staff job performance within the universities can be measured by the extent to which each of their function is maintained towards the university's goals in terms of their ability to meet set deadlines/objectives, teamwork, complete integration and synergy between employees' career goals and alignment to the institution's objectives, growth, sense of identity, social responsibility and flexibility (Hashim, 2019).

Relative Influence of Workplace Safety and Conflict Management on Job Performance of University Non-Teaching Staff in Southwestern Nigeria

From the study that examined the effects of various HRM practices on performance and the moderating effect of CEO support on the relationship between HRM practices and performance. The study employed a survey on 215 Chinese firms. The results indicate a positive relationship between HRM practices and performance and verify the moderating effect of CEO support on the relationship; this study is the first one on demonstrating the moderating effect of CEO support on the relationship between HRM practices and performance in the context of Chinese firms (Rhee et al. 2014).

A researcher looked at the impact of human resource management practices on employee performance in the case of some rural banks in the Ashanti region of Ghana. The findings of the study revealed that human resource practices are improperly planned; implemented and managed by non-human resource experts and that the practices, programs and policies of these rural banks are lowly perceived by their employees. The study also showed that the enormous benefits of properly managing human resources are lost to these rural banks. It was recommended that rural banks should dedicate a department to HR for the proper management of human resources through whom competitive advantage could be created (Quansah, 2013).

Ojo and Abolade (2014) conducted a study on the impact of conflict management on employees' performance in a public sector organisation, and it was established that effective conflict management affects employees' morale positively and influences employees' performance. They further emphasised that proper and appropriate conflict management within an organisation facilitates growth which leads to high level of employees' performance. Successfully managing conflict has a domino effect, by allowing managers to create a workplace where employees can thrive. As established by Beryl (2017) in his study on the influence of conflict management on performance, the scholar revealed that a positive relationship exists between conflict management strategies and employees' performance within organisations.

Hotepo, Asokere, Abuul-Azees and Ajemunigbohun (2010) asserted that "conflicts are part of human nature and it is extremely important to study it not only for theoretical purposes but also for organisational practice" in private, public and political organisations, as well as in judicial and work disputes, in military operations, and many other institutions of learning. They found that the major cause of organisational conflicts was lack of resources within the organisation and that when conflicts are properly managed in an organisation, it will lead to the attainment and achievement of organisational goals and objectives. This means that there is a positive relationship between conflict management and employees' performance. The question arising from the above however is, will the same be obtainable within the university system, particularly among non-teaching staff?

Research Design

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design to sought and establish the relationship that exist between the independent and dependent variables. The study sample was drawn across public universities in southwestern states of Nigeria. This sample, thus drawn, formed the participant respondents in the study on which the research instruments were administered.

Variables in the Study

The independent variable in this study is human resource management practices (work-life balance, conflict management, compensation, capacity building, equal opportunity and workplace safety) while the dependent variable is job performance of senior non-teaching staff which is measured by mastery of job content, output of work, quality of work, prompt responses to official matters, and prompt responses to staff and students' official requests. The instruments covered all the identified variables in the study.

Study Population

The target population of the study consisted of 10,348 senior non-teaching staff of both the federal and state universities in southwestern Nigeria. This population was in focus because of the significant role the senior non-teaching staff plays in the achievement of university goals and objectives. Again, in most universities, the population of the non-teaching staff are more, thus, this population cannot be underplayed in the attainment of universities' vision and mission.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study adopted the multi-stage sampling procedure. In the first stage, the simple random sampling technique was adopted to select of five out of six states which represented eighty percent (80%) of states in Southwestern Nigeria. In the second stage, stratified random sampling technique was used to sort federal and state universities into stratum. Four federal universities were selected out of six and six state universities out of ten universities which represented sixty percent (60%) of universities in Southwestern Nigeria. The third stage involved the selection of senior non-teaching staff in each sampled university using proportionate to size sampling technique. Fifteen percent (15%) of the senior non-teaching staff which is 1,142 respondents were selected out of 7,607 total numbers of senior non-teaching staff as shown in Table 3.2.

Research Instruments

Section 'A' of the instrument contains respondent's demographic data such as sex, academic qualification, type of institution, years of experience on the job, job designation, department and cadre.

Conflict Management Scale

The Conflict management scale was adapted from literature to elicit responses from senior non-teaching staff members on CONTISS 6 to 9. Section B contains 30 items on work-life balance, conflict management, compensation, capacity building, equal opportunity and workplace safety. Conflict management scale is in four Likert scale format consisting of responses of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) which are ranked 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Senior Non-Teaching Staff Job Performance Questionnaire

This Senior Non-Teaching Staff Job Performance Questionnaire was adapted from the harmonised annual performance evaluation reports of sampled public universities to elicit responses from senior non-teaching staff on CONTISS 11 and 13. The questionnaire contains 20 items on the job performance of senior non-teaching staff in terms of their display of mastery of job content, output of their work, quality of work, prompt responses to official matters such as mails, memos, and prompt responses to both staff and students requests. The questionnaire is in five Likert scale format with five options of responses: Excellent (E), Very Good (VG), Good (G), Fair (F) and Poor (P), ranked 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Validity and Reliability of Research Instruments

The appropriateness or the validity of the instruments was determined by the adequacy of the instruments to measure the variables in the study. Face and content validity of these instruments were assessed and assured by the candidate's supervisor, and other experts in the Department of Educational Management, University of Ibadan. The instruments were given back to the researcher's supervisor for final approval after all corrections were made.

The instruments were first pilot tested by administering it to 100 senior non-teaching staff and Deputy Registrars in two different universities in Ekiti State: 50 instruments in a state university, and 50 instruments in a federal university. The respondents at the pilot testing stage were not part of the respondents during the main study because they were drawn from universities that were not selected for the main study, although they have similar characteristics with those selected as sample frame for the study. The instruments were subjected to Cronbach's Alpha reliability test which yielded the following results: Job performance ($r = 0.96$), conflict management scale yielded ($r = 0.958$) and workplace safety showed ($r = 0.927$) questionnaires.

From the above results, all instruments for measuring the variables of human resource management practices had high reliability coefficient indices which showed that the instruments were reliable. Likewise, the senior non-teaching staff job performance questionnaire was subjected to a reliability test using the Cronbach's alpha reliability test and the result yielded ($r = 0.998$). This suggests that the scale has a high reliability index.

Method of Data Analysis

The data were utilised for this study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to answer research question 1, while research question 2 was answered using Multiple Regression Analysis at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relative contribution of human resource management practices of conflict management and workplace safety to job performance of senior non-teaching staff in public universities in Southwestern Nigeria.

Table 1 presents the coefficient tables for all the independent variables.

Table 1 Pearson Product Moment Correlation matrix involving all the Independent and Dependent Variables

Variables	Job. P	Conf. M	WPS
job performance	1.000		
conflict management	0.014	1.000	
workplace safety	0.075*	0.469*	1.000

*denotes significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significant

Table 1 shows that there is no significant relationship between conflict management and job performance ($r = 0.06$; $p > 0.05$) of senior non-teaching staff in public universities in southwestern Nigeria. However, there is a significant relationship between workplace safety and job performance ($r = 0.06$; $p > 0.05$) of senior non-teaching staff in public universities in southwestern Nigeria.

Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing Relative Contributions

Coefficients ^a					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	77.280	3.568		21.662	.000
Conflict Mang.	-.153	.148	-.047	-1.035	NS
Workplace Saf.	-.089	.128	-.040	-.693	NS

a. Dependent Variable: Job Perform.

Key:

NS= Not Significant

S= Significant

Table 2 reveals that there is no significant relative contribution of conflict management to job performance ($\beta = -0.05$; $t = -1.04$; $p > 0.05$), and there is no significant relative contribution of workplace safety to job performance of the senior non-teaching staff ($\beta = -0.04$; $t = -0.69$; $p > 0.05$). Therefore, null hypothesis is not rejected.

DISCUSSION

The finding of the present study reveals that there is no significant relative contribution of conflict management to job performance of senior non-teaching staff of public universities in Southwestern Nigeria, ($\beta = -0.05$; $t = -1.04$; $p > 0.05$). The findings is in disagreement with that of Ojo and Abolade (2014) and Irene (2014) which showed that effective conflict management affects employees’ morale and in turn influence employees’ performance positively in an organisation, Abdul and Sehar Saeed (2015) indicated that there is relative significant effect of conflict management techniques on employees’ performance. All there reports were found to be in opposition to the case in public universities in Southwestern, Nigeria as reflected in table 4.5B with the least $\bar{x} = (2.97)$.

The findings of Koon (2013); Nongmaithem and Biniam (2016), Nnaeto and Ndoh (2018), Sabiu, Kura and Reni (2018), and Onuorah, Okeke, and Ikechukwu (2019) revealed contrary results. They stated that the greater the compensation for staff, the higher their performance and morale, and that compensation management has significant effects on performance all things being equal. These positions are different from the findings of this present study which shows that there is no significant contribution of compensation to the job performance of senior non-teaching staff of public universities in Southwestern Nigeria. The contrary opinions are mainly due to different moderating variables, sample size, contexts, and other yardsticks used in the studies. The findings of Nnorom, et al (2016) was inconclusive about the relative significance of compensation on job performance however, it stressed that workers’ compensation package matters a lot and that organisations embrace the concept of compensation practices but there were difficulty in its execution due to many unforeseen constraints. This may also be the reason there is no significant relative contribution of compensation to the job performance of senior non-teaching staff.

Findings reveal that there is no significant relative contribution of conflict management to job performance ($\beta = -0.05$; $t = -1.04$; $p > 0.05$), and there is no significant relative contribution of workplace safety to job performance ($\beta = -0.04$; $t = -0.69$; $p > 0.05$). Therefore, null hypothesis is not rejected.

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This study reveals that workplace safety has have no significant contribution on the job performance of senior non-teaching staff. This result is consistent with the findings by Inuwa and Muhammad (2016) who revealed a negative significant effect of the moderating variable of physical working environment on employees' performance. This was also supported with the findings of Saka and Salami (2014) as revealed that favourable and conducive work environments were necessary for employees' performance.

Salau, Worlu, Osibanjo, Adeniji, Falola, Olokundun, Ibidunni, Atolagbe, Dirisu and Ogueyungbo (2020) revealed that most offices were dilapidated, without ventilation, no illumination, and poorly furnished. In some cases, many lecturers share offices and this is also applicable to the non-teaching staff which has resulted in no significant effect on their job performance. These results showed a negative contribution of workplace safety on job performance. However, the result of this research is contrary to the study of Bua (2016), who reported that safety practice had a high extent of influence on staff performance of both state and federal universities in North-central states in Nigeria.

The results from this study show that the relationship among conflict management, workplace safety and job performance of senior non-teaching staff in public universities in Southwestern Nigeria differs. The results of the study show that conflict management also has no significant relationship with job performance of senior non-teaching staff in universities in the study area ($r = 0.01$; $p > 0.05$). This finding is in contrary to the findings of Ojo and Abolade (2014); Irene (2014), and Abdul and Sehar Saeed (2015) that proved a significant relationship between conflict management and job performance. Although, this present study has proven that the job performance of senior non-teaching staff is rated very good (mean=3.76) which is 75.2% and not just a function of conflict management practice alone but inclusive other indices of human resource management practices identified in this study. Hence, conflict management practice has no significant relationship with job performance of senior non-teaching staff in selected universities in southwestern Nigeria.

The results of the study reflect a significant relationship between workplace safety and senior non-teaching staff job performance in universities in the study area ($r = 0.08$; $p < 0.05$). This finding is not consistent with the findings of Saka and Salami (2014), Inuwa and Muhammad (2016), and Salau et al (2020) which indicated that there was no significant relationship between workplace safety and job performance.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated relative influence of conflict management and workplace safety on the job performance of senior non-teaching staff in public universities in Southwestern, Nigeria. The findings also indicate that significant relationship exist between conflict management and job performance, but workplace safety is not having positive relationship on the job performance of senior non-teaching staff of public universities as this would invariably lead to the realisation of institutional goals and objectives.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this study:

- I. senior non-teaching staff should be encourage to put in more efforts in their job performance as their salary level increases,
- II. attention should be paid to maintain the practice of conflict management among senior non-teaching staff as it has been proven based on this study that it enhance job performance,

- III. public universities should incorporate and strengthen the use of human resource management practices as identified in this study to further enhance job performance of senior non-teaching staff.

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